

A STUDY ON RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN MOTIVATION, STRESS AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF HIGHER SECONDARY ADOLESCENCE STUDENT

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Paper Received On: 20 JANUARY 2026

Peer Reviewed On: 24 FEBRUARY 2026

Published On: 01 MARCH 2026

Abstract

INTRODUCTION: *Motivation is an internal force that drives us to do something or drives us to do something or any type of act and not stay you calm until the goal you pursue. Its two types Intrinsic motivation (personal interest) and Extrinsic motivation (grades and rewards etc). Psychological Stress is a natural activity from internal and external stressors that can affect people physically and emotionally. Objective of the study is to find out the student's overall motivation and stress level for academic achievement and to find out the relationship between motivation and stress on academic achievement of higher secondary student. Researcher select 30 sample of H.S student from Mundumary high school. and I use random sampling for data collection. And tool use perceived stress scale and academic motivation scale. From the study Researcher find that from 30 student 40% student have high motivation (90% intrinsic and extrinsic motivation and 10% amotivation). 40% student have medium motivation (extrinsic and intrinsic both). And 20% student have amotivation. From 30 student, I found that they have medium stress 15 to 26. Researcher say that when the student has medium stress, they highly motivated for their academic achievement. And when they have much stress, they feel some problem. For this student should medium stress for their high motivation and high academic achievement.*

Keywords: *Stress, Motivation, Academic Achievement, Higher Secondary Student, Adolescent student.*

INTRODUCTION

MOTIVATION: 'Motivation' is a term has been derived from a Latin word 'movere', which mean 'to move'. It can be described in terms of drive, desires, force, needs, which that may lead to individuals behaving in a particular manner motivation has been mainly understand as a factor, that factor drives and pushes someone in a particular direction or to behave in a particular way. Motivation can be termed as a driving force and it can also be stated as a process

that start and drives various activities, whether physical or psychological (Gerring and Zimbardo,2006). Morgan et al (1993, P.268), define motivation as “the driving and pulling forces which result in persistent behaviour directed toward particular goals”. Quick, Nelson, Khandelwal (2013, P.172) defined motivation as “the process of arousing and sustaining goal directed behaviour”. When we discuss upper definition, we find that motivation have 3 main components. 1) drives 2) Needs 3) Incentives (Clark Hull ,1943)

NEEDS: These are biological states of cellular or our bodily deficiencies that work on drives. For example, one individual need water, food, and of course oxygen for survive (Feist and Rosenberg, 2015). This is we called biological needs, also We have cognitive needs include such needs, those are achievement and Curiosity.

- 1) **DRIVES:** Feist and Rosenberg (2015, P.397) define drives as “the perceived states of tension that occur when our bodies are deficient in some need, creating on argue to relieve the tension”.
- 2) **INCENTIVES:** This is external or is form the environment and plays a role in motivating behaviour to the people.

TYPES OF MOTIVATION:

- 1) **EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION:** “Motivation that comes from outside the person and usually involves rewards and praises”. (Feist and Rosenberg,2015 P.415). example: reward, praise, money, feedback etc.)
- 2) **INTRINSIC MOTIVATION:** This type of motivation provides satisfaction / pleasure that the activities / tasks may not provide this motivation increase performance and achievement. (Feist and Rosenberg ,2015 P.415)

STRESS: The term stress has been derived from a Latin word, “Stringer” which mean “to draw fight “(cox, 1978). In 18th century, stress is term of pressure, strain, or force (cartwright and cooper ,1997). In that time people understand that stress as an external stimulus. but latter people understand that stress is responsible to certain disturbance for individual. Baum et al. (1981) defined that stress as a “process in which environmental events or force called stressors, threatens an organism’s existence and wellbeing “. When we discuss about stress, we also discuss about stressors, that can be described as situation, event, person and anything that leads to the stress response. Gerring and Zimbardo (2005, pg. 430) defined stressor as stimulus event that places a demand on an organism for some “kind of adaptive response”. So, one individual has various stress in his/her life. Stress is

a state of mental or emotional tension caused by difficult situation say World Health Organization (WHO).

STRESSOR: something that causes great worry or emotional difficulty or a negative physical effect on the body (Cambridge dictionary). It also be described as varied external and internal stimuli that way led to or increase to the stress. A Stressor is a situation or a event that make stress. Stressor is different type, like physical, psychological, environmental, social and as life events. Stressor also facing frequent challenging situations motivation, as stress often motivates us to work, study in certain direction. Thus, without any stress in life we will not be motivated to perform any kind of work, study, everything. When stress is increased, then it harmful to us, as more salt than required can make food taste bad.

TYPE OF STRESS:

- 1) **EUSTRESS:** When stress is good that time it called Eustress. Eustress can be defined as “good stress, caused by a positive response to a desired stressor, such as a wedding or a new job, or a good mark “. (Truxillo et al (2016, Pg .441).
- 2) **NEUSTRESS:** When stress is not helpful nor harmful, it can be described as ‘Neu stress’ (Schafer (1998, Pg 7).
- 3) **DISSTRESS:** It occurs when the arousal experienced by the individual is very high or very low. (Schafer (1998, Pg 8). This is two types
 - a) **Acute stress** – It is intense but does not last for a prolonged period of time.
 - b) **Chronic stress** – It may not be as intense but may exist for a prolonged.

STRESS, AS A FACTOR OF MOTIVATION:

Most of people say stress is unhealthy but it is not entirely bad for us. Moderate levels of stress can be beneficial for us in several ways that’s are- (Dhruva Koranne, (2022).

- I) **IT HELP ENHANCE OUR PERFORMANCE:**
that is Eustress which increase our performance and academic achievement of the student.
- II) **STRESS MAKE US ALERT:**
Stress also releases different types of hormones like adrenaline, which can boost our energy and our overall level of focus and alertness. And this alertness can help us become more aware of the situation around us, and we take quick action for this.

III) STRESS CAN HELP BUILD RESILIENCE:

Resilience is our ability to cope with difficult situations. When we face stressful situations, we think about it and overcome this situation smartly.

THE DARK SIDE OF STRESS

- I) Reduce physical health
- II) Effects on mood
- III) Burn out

HIGHER SECONDARY ADOLESCENT STUDENT

Higher Secondary Student, they also called plus two student who passed 10th exam, Adolescence student their age 12-18/19/20, and this certain period student face different type of psychological factors like motivation, stress, anxiety, curiosity, interest play a good or vital role for their Academic Achievement which very important for their future. and this period is very important because after this period they gone another important period of life.

ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT

Academic Achievement is a level of success which a student gets in his or her educational life. Like grades, test scores, etc.

So, my topic is “**A Study on Relationship Between Motivation, Stress, and Academic Achievement of Higher Secondary Adolescence Student**”.

2.0 OBJECTIVES:

- i) To find out the stress level and motivation level of higher secondary students by gender.
- ii) To compare the stress level on their academic achievement of higher secondary students by gender.
- iii) To compare the motivation level on their Academic Achievement of higher secondary students by Gender.

3.0 METHEDODOLOGY:

3.1) SAMPLE DETAILS: My samples are 30 students of Higher Secondary school student who read in the school, name Mundarnari Ushananda vidyapith (H.S), which situated in Mundarnari, Kharagpur, Paschim Medinipur. Out of **30 students**, I have 15 girl’s student and 15 boys’ students. For sample Collection I use random sampling.

3.2) TOOL: In this study, I use two questionnaires as a tool. First One is Perceived stress Scale for data collection. The perceived stress Scale (PSS) is a classic assessment instrument. The tool, while originally developed in 1983, remains a popular choice for helping us understand how different situations affect our feelings and our perceived stress. The

questions in this scale ask about your feelings and thoughts during the last month. In each case, you will be asked to indicate how often you felt or thought a certain way. Although some of the questions are similar, there are differences between them and you should treat each one as a separate question. The best approach is to answer fairly quickly. that is, do not try to count up the number of times you felt a particular way, rather indicate the alternative that seems like a reasonable estimate for each question choose from the following alternatives: "0- never, 1- almost never, 2- sometimes, 3- fairly often (4) - very often. one person can determine his/her PSS score by following these directions:

First, reverse your scores for questions 4,5, 7 and 8. On these 4 questions, change the scores like this: 0=4, 1=3, 2=2, 3=1, 4=0, Now add up your scores for each item to get a total and find student condition. Individual scores on the PSS can range from 0 to 40 with higher scores indicating higher perceived Stress. Scores ranging from 0-13 would be considered low stress. Scores ranging from 14-26 would be considered moderate stress. Scores ranging from 27-40 would be considered high perceived stress. 2nd One Academic Motivation Scale (AMS-C28) for measuring why one student want to go to college. And what way it is increase their academic achievement. And this questionnaire has 28 questions .and all question have 7 response, 1 does not correspond at all, 2 and 3 – corresponds a little, 4- correspond moderately, 5 and 6 – correspond a lot, and 7 is correspond exactly. From 28 questions,

2,9,16,23- Intrinsic Motivation -To know

6,13,20,27 – Intrinsic Motivation – toward accomplishment

4,11,18,25 – Intrinsic motivation – to experience stimulation

3,10,17,24 – Extrinsic motivation – Identified

7, 14, 21, 28 – Extrinsic Motivation – Introjected

1, 8, 15, 22 – Extrinsic Motivation – External regulation.

5,12,19,26 – Amotivation.

4.0 RESULT:

TABLE-1
STRESS OF GIRLS

Range of Stress	Number	Percentage
14-18	4	26.66
19-23	7	46.66
24-28	1	6.66
29-33	3	20
34-38	0	0

Total	15	100
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TABLE-2
STRESS OF BOYS

Range of Stress	Number	Percentage
14-18	3	20
19-23	8	53.33
24-28	2	13.33
29-33	1	6.66
34-38	1	6.66
Total	15	100

TABLE- 3
TABLE OF GIRLS AND BOYS STRESS

Range of Stress	Percentage of girl's stress	Percentage of boy's stress
14-18	26.66	20
19-23	46.66	53.33
24-28	6.66	13.33
29-33	20	6.66
34-38	0	6.66

TABLE- 4
ACADEMIC MOTIVATION OF GIRLS

Range of Academic Motivation	Number	Percentage
85-100	2	13.33
101-116	10	66.67
117-132	1	6.67
133-148	0	0
149-164	2	13.33

TABLE-5
ACADEMIC MOTIVATION OF BOYS

Range of Academic Motivation	Number	Percentage
85-100	3	20
101-116	7	46.67
117-132	4	26.66
133-148	1	6.66
149-164	0	0

5.0 FINDINGS

- I) From first Objectives, I find that The Range of Stress is 14 to 18, 19 to 23, 24-28, 29-33 and 34 to 38. The girls have percentage of stress is similarly 26.66, 46.66, 6.66, 20, and 0.
- II) Also, First Objectives, I find that, the range of stress is continuously 14-18, 19-23, 24-28, 29 – 33 and 34-38. The boys have percentage of stress is similarly 20, 53.33, 13.33, 6.66 and 6.66.
- III) From table 3, I find that Percentage of girl's stress compare to percentage of boy's stress. Like, in 14 to 18 range Percentage of girl's stress is 26.66 and boy stress is 20. Also in 19-23, girls have 46.66 and boys have 53.33, In 24 to 28 girls have 6.66 and boys have 13.33, In 29 to 33 girls have 20 and boys have 6.66. In 34 to 38 girls have 0 and boys have 6.66 percentage stress.
- IV) From table 4 regarding Academic Motivation of girls, the range of Academic Motivation is 85 to 100, 101 to 116, 117 to 132, 133 to 148, and 149 to 164. The girls have percentage of Academic Motivation is similarly 13.33%, 66.67%. 6.67%. 0%, 13.33%.
- V) From table 5, regarding Academic Motivation of boy, in same range of academic motivation, boys have percentage of Academic motivation is 20%, 46.67%, 26.66%, 6.66%.
- VI) From table 6, I find that percentage of girl academic motivation compare to percentage of boy academic motivation, like in 85 to 100 range girls have 66.67, and boys have 46.67, 117 to 132, girls have 6.67% and boys have 26.66 %, In 133 to 148, girl have 0 percentage and boys have 6.66%, In 149 to 164 range girls have 13.33% and boys have 0 % percentage.

6.0 DISCUSSION

From 100 % girls, 26.66% girls have 14 to 18 stress which is low moderate and 46.66 % girls have 19 to 23 stress which is high moderate and 6.66 percent girls have 24 to 28 stress which is low high stress and 20% girls have moderate high stress, that is 29 to 33stress.

From 100% boys, 20 % boy have 14 to 18 stress which is moderate low, and 53.33 % boys have 19 to 23 stress which is moderately high, and 13.33 percent boys have 24 to 28 stress which is low high stress, and 6.66% student have 29 to 33 stress that

is moderately high stress and 6.66% student have very high stress, that is 34 to 38 %.

From 100% boys, 20 % boy have 14 to 18 stress which is moderate low, and 53.33% boys have 19 to 23 stress which is moderately high and 13.33 % boys have 24 to 28 stress which is low high stress, and 6.66% student have 29 to 33 stress that is moderately high stress and 6.66% student have very high stress, that is 34 to 38%. From 100 % girls and 100 % boys, in 14 to 18 stress girls have 26.66% stress which is more than from boys (20%). In 19 to 23 stress boys have 53.33% stress which is more than from girls (46.66 %). In 24 to 28 stress girls have 6.66% which is less than from boys (13.33%). In 29 to 33 girls have 20 % stress which is greater than from boys (6.66%). In 34 to 38 stress girls have no stress but boys have 6.66% stress.

From 100% girls, 13.33% have 85 to 100 academic motivation which is low moderate academic and 66.67 % have 101 to 116 academic motivation which high moderate. 6.67 % girls have 117 to 132 academic motivation which is low high Academic Motivation, and no girls have 133 to 148 Academic motivation. And 13.33% girls have 149 to 164 Academic Motivation which is high academic motivation.

From 100% boys, 20 % have 85 to 100 academic motivation which is low moderate academic motivation and 46.67 % have 101 to 116 academic motivation which high moderate. 26.67 % boys have 117 to 132 academic motivation which is low moderate Academic Motivation, and 6.67% boys have 133 to 148 Academic motivation which is very low and no boys have 149 to 164 Academic motivation.

7.0 CONCLUSION

- 80% girls have moderate stress and 25% girls have high stress.
- 73% boys have moderate stress and 13% boys have high moderately stress. 13 % boys have high stress.
- In this time boys and girls both have moderate stress for their study.
- 70% girls have low moderate academic motivation and 15 % girls have high academic motivation.
- 67% boys have low moderate academic motivation and 33% boys have high moderate academic motivation.

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